

The Study of Serum Uric Acid Levels as an Indicator of Outcome among Acute Ischaemic Stroke

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Abstract:

Background: Association between serum uric acid (SUA) and the outcome of acute ischemic stroke is debated and needs to be evaluated. The present study was conducted to study the serum uric acid concentration as an indicator of outcome among acute ischaemic stroke and to determine the role of serum uric acid as a risk factor for acute ischemic stroke.

Methods: An observational study where 80 patients who presented within 48 hours of onset of stroke admitted to medical wards/ICU of MG hospital Bhilwara were selected for the study.

Results: Out of 80 patients included for the study, Majority were male (68.7%) and 54.5% of the males and 52.0% of females showed raised serum uric acid levels. 34 out of 80 patients were diabetic (i.e. 42.5%) Among them 18 had raised serum uric acid (ie.52.9%), 58.8% of the patients were hypertensive and among them 55.3% were found to have raised serum uric acid, 29 out of 50 patients had bad outcome, with elevated uric acid levels found 21 among them. In the present study, outcome of Stroke were significantly associated with Serum Uric acid levels.

Conclusions: Serum uric acid levels can be used as a prognostic indicator as a marker for increased risk of stroke.

Keywords: Ischemic stroke, Outcome, Serum uric acid.

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Introduction

The cerebrovascular accident is one of the most common and leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide and it is only second to myocardial infarction accounting for up to 165,000 deaths per year in the United States [1]. The collective incidence of stroke ranges from 105 to 152/100,000 persons per year in India [2].

Stroke is defined by (WHO) World Health Organization as 'a clinical syndrome consisting of rapidly developing clinical signs of focal (or global in case of coma) disturbance of cerebral function lasting more than 24 hour or leading to death with no apparent cause other than a vascular origin.' A transient ischaemic attack (TIA) is defined as stroke symptoms and signs that resolve within 24 hours [3]. Uric acid is an end product of purine metabolism in humans, is known to be relation with many systemic risk factors of stroke, such as

hypertension, diabetes mellitus, insulin resistance and obesity [4]. The plasma concentration of uric acid is almost 10-fold higher than other antioxidants such as Vitamin C and Vitamin E. It is considered that uric acid has much higher antioxidant capacity [5]. Uric acid which is formed by catabolism of purine is proposed to neutralize the free radical injury that occurs in ischemic stroke. Epidemiological studies have suggested a direct relationship between the levels of the natural antioxidant uric acid and the risk of cerebrovascular and coronary ischaemic events [6-7].

There are few studies conducted in Indian scenario, which shows the role of serum uric acid in cases of acute ischaemic stroke. There is a need to study the severity and clinical outcome of stroke patients with respect to their uric acid levels in the blood.

Hence the present study has been undertaken to analyse the severity and clinical outcome of stroke patients with respect to their serum uric acid levels at the time of admission.

Material and Methods

It was an Observational Prospective study conducted among 80 cases of acute ischaemic stroke admitted in medicine ward and ICU at MG hospital Bhilwara over the period of 6 months, who fulfilled inclusion criteria were included in our study.

Patients with more than 18 years, with CT brain / MRI brain confirmed cases of acute ischaemic stroke were included in the present study. Whereas, Patients with known case of cardio-embolic stroke, Past history of valvular heart disease, Patients receiving drugs which are likely to alter levels of serum uric acid (diuretics, Losartan, Allopurinol), Malignancy, Renal or liver dysfunction were excluded from the present study.

All the required details about cases such as demographic data (Age, gender, address, registration number, etc.), clinical presentations (signs and symptoms), general examination findings, and systemic examination findings were carried out. Investigations like complete hemogram; renal profile, Serum uric acid and Lipid profile were performed wherever necessary.

All stroke cases and patients were assigned into two groups based on serum uric acid levels (normal serum uric acid group and elevated serum uric acid group). Serum uric acid was measured when the patient was admitted and was correlated with functional recovery of the patients after 4 weeks. Patients were reviewed 4 weeks after onset of stroke and were stratified using Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOS).

Glasgow Outcome Scale

1. Indicates death
2. Vegetative state (patients is unable to interact with environment)

3. Severe disability (patient is unable to live independently but can follow commands)
4. Moderate disability (Patients is capable of living independently but unable to return to work or school).
5. Mild or No disability (Patient can return to work or school).

Scale 4 and 5 - Favourable outcome

Scale 1, 2 & 3 - Unfavourable outcome

Statistical Analysis

All the data was recorded with the help of standard case record proforma and were entered into Excel spread sheet sequentially (MS Excel). Statistical analysis was carried out with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. Descriptive analysis was carried out by mean and standard deviation for quantitative variables, frequency and proportion for categorical variables. Chi-square/Fisher-Exact test was used to find the significance of study parameters on categorical scale and continuous scale between two groups. The p-value <0.05 is suggestive of statistical significance.

Results

In the present study total of 80 cases were included, majority of the population were male (68.7%) and 31.3% was female. The mean age group of the population in the present study was 56.4 years. Elevated uric acid was found in 43 (53.7%) cases.

Table-1 shows basic demographic details and Table-2 shows the distribution of the demographic and risk factors among the acute stroke patients with normal serum uric acid group and elevated serum uric acid group i.e., the percentage of population in both normal and elevated serum uric acid groups based on different variables like gender, diabetes, hypertension, smoking, were almost similar as there was no statistical difference between normal and elevated serum uric acid groups.

Table 1: Showing the baseline demographic data.

Variable	N (%)	
Gender	Male	55 (68.7%)
	Female	25 (31.3%)
Medical history	Diabetes	34 (42.5%)
	Hypertension	47 (58.8%)
	Smoking	32 (40.0%)

Table 2: Uric acid and its association with risk factors

	Normal uric acid group (n=37)		Elevated uric acid group (n=43)	
	N	%	N	%
Female	12	32.4%	13	30.2%
Male	25	67.6%	30	69.8%
Chi-square = 0.001 with 1 degree of freedom; P = 0.976				

Diabetic	16	43.2%	18	41.9%
Non-diabetic	21	56.8%	25	58.1%
Chi-square = 0.010 with 1 degree of freedom; P = 0.919				
Hypertensive	21	56.8%	26	60.5%
Non-hypertensive	16	43.2%	17	39.5%
Chi-square = 0.012 with 1 degree of freedom; P = 0.914				
Smoker	15	40.5%	17	39.5%
Non-smoker	22	59.5%	26	60.5%
Chi-square = 0.019 with 1 degree of freedom; P = 0.891				

51 out of 80 (63.7%) patients had good outcome, among them elevated uric acid levels was found in 22 (43.1%). The association between serum uric acid level and outcome was found to be statistically significant (Chi-square = 5.251 with 1 degree of freedom; P = 0.022).

Figure 1: Uric acid level and Outcome

Discussion

The objective for the present study was to correlate between levels of serum uric acid and outcome of ischaemic stroke. 80 patients of acute ischaemic stroke admitted in medicine ward and ICU at MG Hospital Bhilwara, who fulfilled inclusion criteria, were included in the study.

In the present study, the gender distribution 68.7% of the study population were males and 31.3% of them were female, a similar study done by Chiquete E et al., showed a gender distribution of 52% males and 48% females [8].

The present study had a male predominance; this can be attributed to the presence of additional risk factors for stroke like smoking, and alcohols. There were no significant statistical difference, when serum uric acid levels between males and females were compared (p value >0.05).

In the present study, the mean age included was 56.4 years, a similar study done by Balaji B and Srinivas B the mean age of the study population was 60.58 years [9]. This increased incidence of

stroke in elderly can be attributed to the fact that the age acts as an independent risk factor for ischaemic stroke. 34 out of 80 patients had diabetes (42.5%) as diagnosed by Fasting Blood Sugar more than 125 mg%. One of the bad prognostic factors in the outcome of stroke is the presence of associated diabetes mellitus. In a study by Nishkanen et al, serum uric acid levels were a strong predictor of stroke in Type II diabetes [10]. The tests of significance didn't find any correlation between uric acid and diabetes (p value >0.05).

Hypertension is one of the major risk factor for development of stroke. In present study analysis of study subjects presented with hypertension at the time of admission carried out. In our study 47 patients were hypertensive i.e.58.8%. Among them 26 had raised serum uric acid levels i.e., 55.3% of the hypertensive patients. Tushar Patil et al and Milionis et al quoted SUA levels were higher in hypertensive compared to non-hypertensive [11-12].

The standard Chi-square test proved that there is no statistically significant association between

hypertension and raised serum uric acid levels (p value >0.05). In our study, 32 patients were smokers (40%). Among those 32 patients, 17 had elevated uric acid levels. By applying Chi-square test, P value was not significant, (>0.05) implicating no correlation between smoking and raised uric acid levels. Angel Chamorro et al in his study has also proved that uric acid levels are independent of smoking. However associated atherosclerosis can elevate the uric acid levels falsely giving an impression that smoker having elevated uric acid levels [13]. 36.3% of the total patients under study group had poor outcome. Out of which 72.4% had raised serum uric acid levels. The standard Chi square test was applied and it proved the statistical significance (p value <0.05) between poor outcome and raised uric acid levels. Prasad et al, reported that Mean SUA in expired cases was significantly higher than survived [14]. According to Chamorro et al., uric acid is a potent anti-oxidant and hence it elevates as a compensatory mechanism in ischaemic tissues to protect the brain from free radical injury [13].

However it has been evident by experiments that uric acid is synthesized locally from infarcted tissues, particularly during reperfusion. So its level in serum rises often in proportion to the size of the infarcted tissue, reperfusion status and the extent of the free radical injury.

Conclusion

Serum uric acid levels can be used as a prognostic indicator for increased risk of stroke. Elevated serum urate concentration may stratify risk of death after acute stroke. Anti-oxidants can be added as a part of treatment protocol in patients with acute ischaemic stroke. Also, trial of serum uric acid lowering drugs in stroke patients as well as in those at increased risk of stroke can be worth considering. Further long term prospective studies are needed to establish the role of serum uric acid in ischemic stroke.

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